

winters are extremely cold in the hills (temperature often below 0 °C), only a few of the overwintering larvae survive. High infestations are caused mainly by the second generation larvae resulting from the mass egg laying during Jul-Aug. □

Chemical control of rice stem borers (SB) in the Punjab

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Three SB species—*Scirpophaga incertulas*, *S. innotata*, and *Sesamia inferens*—damage rice in the Punjab. *S. incertulas* is predominant. Damage has been recorded in rice nurseries in certain pockets of Amritsar, Ferozpur, and Faridkot districts.

SB incidence has increased during the last 2 yr. Staggered sowing over a longer period, an increase in the area under irrigation, growing unapproved susceptible varieties, and other agronomic manipulations appear to be

Effect of different insecticides on incidence of rice SB.^a Punjab, India.

Insecticide	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Incidence (% whiteheads)	Yield (t/ha)
Cartap hydrochloride 4 G	1.5	3.8 a	5.3 a
Chlorpyrifos 10 G	1.0	26.4 bed	3.2 d
Carbofuran 3 G	1.0	25.4 bc	4.2 b
Chlorpyrifos 40 EC	0.5	20.2 b	4.2 b
Deltamethrin + buprofezin 5.9 EC	0.09	33.3 d	3.1 d
Phosalone 35 EC	0.5	26.1 bed	3.8 c
Control	—	32.3 cd	2.4 e

^aIn a column, values designated by different letters are statistically different (Duncan's multiple range test).

factors in the increase.

Control of SB is with insecticides. We evaluated two new granular compounds, chlorpyrifos 10 G and cartap hydrochloride 4 G, with carbofuran 3 G as the standard. Chlorpyrifos 40 EC, deltamethrin + buprofezin 5.9 EC, and phosalone 35 EC as foliar spray also were evaluated.

Recommended variety PR103 was grown in 17-m² plots in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Single applications of chemicals were given the first week of Sep 1986, when the crop was nearly 40 d old and when deadhearts reached 5%.

Among the granular insecticides, cartap hydrochloride was most effective (see table). Average whitehead incidence was only 3.8%, compared to 25.4% with carbofuran and 26.4% with chlorpyrifos 10 G. Foliar application of chlorpyrifos 40 EC showed 20.2% incidence, significantly lower than deltamethrin + buprofezin but statistically equal to phosalone.

The significantly highest yield was with cartap hydrochloride. Cartap hydrochloride 4 G granular insecticide at 1.5 kg ai/ha controlled rice SB and promoted yield. □

Monitoring susceptibility of rice pests to insecticides

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Following FAO/IRRI workshops—“Judicious and Efficient Use of Insecticides on Rice” (1983) and “Monitoring Susceptibility Levels of Rice Pests to Insecticides” (1984)—12

Asian rice-growing countries formed a network to establish baseline insecticide susceptibility of major rice pests.

Susceptibility to insecticides was determined by topical application with the Kiya hand-operated microapplicator and a calibrated microsyringe. A specified volume of insecticides for each test insect was applied on the thoracic tergites (Table 1). Treated insects were transferred through a funnel to minimize mechanical damage to plastic tumbler cages containing 8-10 2-wk-old TN1 seedlings.

Larvae were transferred to petri dishes lined with moistened filter paper and provided with cut leaves or diet for stem borer. The tests usually had 3 replications, with at least 15 insects/replication. Cages and petri dishes were kept in an incubator or controlled room at 25-30 °C, 60-80% relative humidity, and 12-h light. Larval

mortality was recorded 24, 48, and 72 h after treatment. LD₅₀/LD₉₅ values of the insecticides were computed using probit analysis.

Five countries have established susceptibility baseline data for *N. lugens* (Table 2). Indonesia had relatively higher LD₅₀ values with three insecticides, indicating that *N. lugens* in Indonesia may be less susceptible to insecticides. However, *N. lugens* from two collection sites did not show much

Table 1. Rice insect pests and volume of insecticides applied.

Insect pest	Volume applied (μl)
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i>	1.0
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	0.5
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	0.2
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	0.1
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	0.1

Table 2. Susceptibility levels of rice pests to insecticides in some rice-growing countries in Asia.

Insect species	Country	Location	LD ₅₀ values (µg/individual)				
			Carbaryl	Carbofuran	Diazinon	Malathion	Monocrotophos
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	India	Lab culture, Hyderabad	0.007	0.002	—	—	—
	Sri Lanka	Lab culture, CARI	—	—	—	—	0.008
	Thailand	Pathumthani	0.005	0.0007	—	0.07	0.004
		Phitsanulok	0.005	0.0004	—	0.09	0.003
	Indonesia	Sleman, Yogyakarta	0.005	0.0008	0.08	0.2	—
		Boyolali, Central Java	0.006	0.001	0.09	0.2	—
Japan	Tikugo, Hukuoka-ken	0.01	0.002	0.07	0.2	—	
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	India	Cuttack	—	—	0.01	—	—
<i>N. cincticeps</i>	Japan	Tikugo, Hukuoka-ken	—	—	0.6	15.2	—
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	Sri Lanka	Alawwa	—	—	—	—	0.003
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i>	China	Changping, Beijing	0.3	0.07	—	0.3	0.3

difference in susceptibility level. LD₅₀ values from two collection sites in Thailand were comparable, indicating

the same susceptibility levels.

India and Japan gave susceptibility data for *N. virescens* and *N. cincticeps*.

The data for *C. medinalis* came from Sri Lanka, and those for *C. suppressalis* from China. □

Water management

Influence of planting method and irrigation practices on rice water requirement

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We studied the irrigation requirement of direct seeded and transplanted rice during 1986 dry season. Two methods of crop establishment were main plot treatments and 3 irrigation schedules (continuous shallow submergence with 5 ± 2 cm water, intermittent irrigation at 5-d intervals with 5 cm water except during flowering, and moderate stress) were subplot treatments. The test variety was IR36.

Soil texture varied from sandy loam to sandy clay loam and alluvium type Mahanadi River soil with pH 5.5. The water table was 40-60 cm deep during the crop duration.

Differences in grain yield due to irrigation schedules and method of planting and their interactions were significant (Table 1). The transplanted crop gave about 36% higher yield than the direct seeded crop. Continuous shallow submergence gave significantly

Table 1. Effect of moisture regime on yield of IR36 under direct seeded and transplanted conditions. Cuttack, India, 1986 dry season.

Moisture regime	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Direct seeded	Transplanted	Mean
Continuous shallow submergence (5 ± 2 cm) (I ₁)	5.1	6.2	5.6
Intermittent irrigation at 5-d intervals (I ₂)	3.3	5.2	4.2
Moderate stress (I ₃)	3.0	4.1	3.6
Mean	3.7	5.2	
LSD to compare irrigation schedules (I)			6.0
LSD to compare method of planting (MP)			3.4
LSD to compare MP at the same level of (I)			5.8
LSD to compare I at the same level of MP			7.3
CV (%)			
MP			32.8
Irrigation schedule and interaction			22.5

higher yield than the two other water treatments. Reduced water application progressively reduced yield, with moderate stress giving the lowest yield.

Yield reduction due to less irrigation water in the intermittent flooding treatment was pronounced under direct seeded conditions. There was not much scope for further yield reduction under moderate stress. On the other hand, yield differences were significant between the two lower water regimes under transplanted conditions.

Irrigation requirements are presented in Table 2. The irrigation water required to maintain continuous shallow

Table 2. Water used by different irrigation treatments. Cuttack, India, 1986 dry season.

Water regime	Water requirement (mm)	
	Direct seeded crop	Transplanted crop
Continuous submergence	2250	2000
Intermittent irrigation	1100	950
Moderate stress	800	750

submergence was more than two times that required for intermittent irrigation. □